

ELECTRONIC COMMERCE SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This article " digital of the " economy " category definition and him to develop different approaches given. Digital of the economy one part calculated electron of commerce essence, classification and electron in commerce transactions where in order structure according to the word is brogan. Electronic commerce development according to offer and recommendations work released.*

Keywords: *electronic commerce, e-commerce platform, online stores, blockchain, electronic contract, IT technologies, transaction, electronic message, electronic motor, electronic document.*

INTRODUCTION

Last in years information technologies and global Internet development significant growth a person of life different in the fields new of directions appear to be take came. Electronic commerce current At the time of the Internet society diary to his life high speed with come in came and his indispensable to the part is spinning.

Electronic commercial term too wide concept to him many definitions given Quoted definitions mostly via the internet done increased each how to trade or to the transaction electron it is called commercial.

Electronic commerce when you say computer networks using done to be increased all financial and trade operations and such operations with dependent business processes own into received economy field is understood.

METHODS

Electronic commerce electron praises done increase, customers and delivered givers search, advertising distribution, internet applications through goods buy get and sell such as many business operations to perform possibility gives. Electronic of commerce this type past appeared in the 60s of the century to be despite the last ten year global changes within happened is giving Global information and cheap digital of gadgets appear to be population number increased going electron of commerce fast of possibilities use enable gives. Electronic of commerce advantages about the following to say can: Time and alive work expenses with depends transaction expenses reduction; For purchases, payments fast input, desired from the place and desired comfortable at the time access opportunity; Client to himself comfortable time, place and at speed the product choose and buy get opportunity have Trade activities the work activity with together in parallel, that is work from release not separated without take to go opportunity; A lot numerous of buyers one of time in itself one how many to firms appeal do it get opportunity; Necessary products at speed looking for to find and this products there is has been to businesses appeal in doing technique and from vehicles efficient use opportunity; of the buyer to live place, health and material supply from the level strictly look everyone row equal to entitled product buy get opportunity; Current of the day there is the world standards answer giving products choose and sell opportunity; Electronic in commerce trade organize to do of enterprises competition strengthens, from monopoly emits and of products quality increase opportunity gives.

Electronic this is commercial online buy get and sell process. These funds and data electron network through transmitted business deal So, physical and digital of products all types sell and services of the deal two participant in the middle organize will be done. This to the participants according to, electron commerce one how many kind of deals own into takes:

- Business for business (B2B)
- To the client business (B2C)
- To the client buyer (C2C)

Electronic commerce companies and to individuals this huge to the market to join and each two towards too big for advantages have has been trade from the model used without own businesses to develop possibility gave. This business of the model main benefit is convenience. Electronic commerce each always works 24 hours a day, a week seven day. That's it means that buyers the work hours, to location how reached to go and the like things without thinking, the product when convenient to get can.

RESULTS

Electronic of commerce objects and subjects, their right and obligations clarified, transactions done increase and their performance provide mechanisms marked, electronic trade to the fields and electron to the contract requirements, goods deliver and praises done increase issues, contract conditions refusal to perform order and electron in commerce export done increase features determined given.

Electronic commerce with valid to legislation according to realization of goods (works, services). to do to the right have entrepreneurship subjects to engage in possible being, in this electron commerce with engagement for addition permission reach feature have document is not required.

Electronic in commerce electron documents on paper formalized and own hand with signed to documents is equalized.

Electronic in commerce contract parties in the middle contract conditions electron documents and messages confirmation the way with agreement through electron document in the form of will be formalized.

Electronic in commerce sellers of the following consists of:

Electronic trade on the field goods (works and services) retail or wholesale sell according to activity done increasing legal persons and alone in order entrepreneurs;

Electronic trade on the field retail goods (works, services) sell according to activity done increasing himself booked by himself persons.

In the field payments the following in methods done is increased:

- Cash money funds with
- Money funds from the bank account transfer through;
- Electronic of money used without

Trade of the fields operators, payment services delivered givers and goods delivered to give services showing legal persons own information to systems or "escrow" service to bank accounts current reach can.

Goods for client by payment done increase during the "exrou" service showing paid money funds client goods of receipt confirmation to be taken until storage to the right have. If the goods delivered if not given or to the description suitable if not, "exrou" service showing money funds to

the buyer returns. If the goods audience by acceptance done if so, money funds of the seller to the account will be held.

Information for, escrow service this financial deal is then the third towards in agreement participant two towards for necessary was payment funds, agreement complete done to increase until, in itself storage and to manage own undertake takes This is it in turn money conditional storage account in the number holding stand up through, agreement more safe to be possibility creates. Payment reliable of the company control under only of the contract all conditions when done openable safe account in the number is stored.

The following electron of commerce main principles is:

- electron in commerce entrepreneurship activities done increase freedom;
- electron in commerce transactions to compose optionality;
- electron in commerce participation reach conditions equality;
- electron commerce of subjects rights and legal interests protection to do
- documents, that's it including electron documents (messages) one diversification;
- information safety provide;
- of goods (works and services), relevant quality provide;
- electron commerce in the field openness, transparency and precision
- Electronic in commerce transactions optional basically is made.
- Electronic deal conditions of the parties at will according to is determined.

Electronic trade the pitch is organizational, informational and technical of decisions software -hardware set, that's it including sale of goods (works, services). for information system through vendor and mutual buyer (customer). Cooperation designated as an online store that provides;

Electronic message is this information the sender identification possible giver electron form note done marked as information;

Electronic the tool is electron in the form information again work, save and him to exchange intended computer and (or) other technical tool, as well telecommunications marked as a network;

Electronic contract is this trade of goods (works, services). for information from systems used without vendor and client in the middle to be built defined as a contract;

Electronic the document is in electronic form note electronic digital signature know approved and electronic document him identification enable giving another to the props have has been information.

DISCUSSION

" Electronic commerce about " under Article 9 of the Act electron documents and electron in the form note done data, their electron address (e-mail so-called messages) to identify possibility gives, to paper based on documents with legal in force recognized as equal, also signed and transactions evidence as use can. Current at the time of Uzbekistan valid in UNCITRAL documents on the law that it was as, electron commerce within paper documents and electron messages between equality set placed.

Information technologies on a global scale development economy and in society changes for lever became of these processes main structural from the parts one of the Internet of the

economy all networks come in is going. Last sometimes through the Internet commerce connections scope significant level expands, it is the following structural parts own into takes:

- via the internet goods sell and buy get
- electron from networks use through money funds transfer
- electron in the form information trade and others

Electronic commerce modern in economics very with high temp developing from fields is one to him one by one of the company digital technologies and they are giving to benefits based, profit which brings activity as is considered. new commerce environment attraction done buyers known opportunities and to benefits have will be Organizations in front standing tasks information and communication technologies of possibilities used without much fast and the most less cost with solution is being done.

Electronic commerce development opportunities evaluation for not only to the Internet connection and of organizations modern computers with technical equipment, perhaps website and electron mail address availability is also large important have. Organization personal website electron economic relationships participants between mutually contact opportunities significant level extends:

- site organization activity with dependent useful information announcement does: analysis and market news, statistics research, trends, customers with of communication to himself special features of this theoretical and practical basics;

- business, organization news placed;

- portfolio to the site or product image will be placed. Consumer offer being carried out goods looks like this announcement done quality, features confirms the company professionalism shows;

- electron in the form information trade and others;

- site to the consumer company with contact installation opportunity gives On the site present done or present being carried out goods and services on the surface public his opinion determination for they ask to pass possible;

- to advertising, of the company to himself and to the product relationship

- fast order

Highlight that's right, the republic scale online of purchases most of them local from stores done is increased.

CONCLUSION

Digital economy when you say only Blockchain technology and of them international finance in the markets use issues or cryptocurrencies to understand need not. Of course, Blockchain technology, cryptocurrencies are also digital of the economy one piece. But digital economy (Digital Economy) means digital communications, using IT take to go economy is understood. In this case, hidden to the economy I'm done to give tool also viewed as can Because first, all operations electron register to the transition, secondly transparent to be is achieved. In addition, in release new IT technologies application because of product and of services cost decreases. Electronic commerce this each two towards benefit for which brings tired activity type is considered Electronic in commerce deals each two towards have come without contract is made and composed contract paper contract with equalized.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Axborot texnologiyalari va kommunikatsiyalari sohasini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi 19.02.2018 dagi PF-5349 sonli farmoni (Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan № PF-5349 dated 19.02.2018 "On measures to further improve the field of information technology and communications") <https://lex.uz/docs/-3564970>
2. Nodir Jumayev O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisi Qonunchilik palatasi deputati nutqi (Speech by Nodir Jumayev, Deputy of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan)
3. <https://review.uz/uz/post/raqamli-iqtisodiyot-mamlakatimiz-taraqqiyotigarovidir>
4. <https://uzreport.news/politics>.